

Identifying Politically Connected Firms: A Machine Learning Approach

VITEZSLAV TITL^{1,2,3}, DENI MAZREKAJ^{3,4,5}, AND FRITZ SCHILTZ³

1. Utrecht University, School of Economics.
2. Charles University, Faculty of Law, Department of Economics.
3. KU Leuven, Leuven Economics of Education Research.
4. Utrecht University, Department of Sociology.
5. University of Oxford, Nuffield College.

Summary

- Using data from Czechia, this paper shows that machine learning algorithms identified politically connected firms with an accuracy of over 85%.
 - Politically connected firms can generate substantial economic and welfare costs for society.
 - Relevance extends beyond Czechia, considering limited data requirements to build the predictive model.
 - This approach could significantly increase the efficiency and effectiveness of government agencies combatting corruption.
 - Ongoing efforts are needed to address biases and firms' adaptability while maintaining a balance between targeted and random audits.
-

1. Introduction

In the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic's second wave, a troubling revelation emerged in a report from the British National Audit Office (2020) in November 2020. The report disclosed that more than half of the public contracts, totaling £10.5 billion, for essential personal protective equipment (PPE) like masks and gloves were awarded without competitive tenders. Shockingly, nearly a third of these suppliers had political or senior official affiliations and were given preferential treatment, making them ten times more likely to secure contracts compared to the regular competitive channel (Conn & Evans, 2020). Some of these suppliers had no prior experience in providing PPE, exemplified by a £108 million contract awarded to a chocolate wholesaler (Archer, 2020). Additionally, documentation explaining supplier selection was often missing, and contracts were finalized after work had already commenced (Pegg, Lawrence, & Conn, 2020). Instances of political connections between politicians and private-sector entities are not isolated, but they occur globally. While not all such connections indicate wrongdoing, they underscore the importance of transparency in political affiliations, particularly as the number of people and firms involved continues to rise, while audit budgets remain stagnant or decrease.

This policy brief highlights the issue by discussing the usage employing supervised machine learning algorithms to predict political connections in Czechia. Czechia uniquely offers publicly available information on political connections, setting it apart from countries like France, Portugal, Canada, and the United States. Using web scrapers and matching algorithms, data was consolidated

to identify politically connected firms based on political donations, board members' donations, and board members' political office runs. About 5% of firms were politically connected, a figure comparable to the U.S. proportion.

The underlying article¹ for this policy brief, unlike prior literature (Decarolis & Giorgiantonio, 2022; Gallego, Rivero, & Martinez, 2021), constructs a novel dataset that measures actual political connections, enabling predictions at the level of these connections, transcending aggregated and contract-level data. This innovative approach advances our ability to understand and address the complex issue of political connections between firms and politicians.

2. Data and methods

The dataset used in the underlying academic article encompasses all firms registered in Czechia in 2018 and their financials and information about political connections of these firms.

As for predictor variables, the dataset was sourced from the Orbis database by Bureau van Dijk, which includes standardized annual accounts, financial ratios, sectoral activities, and ownership information. Furthermore, information about the value of public procurement contracts supplied by the firms and the value of subsidies from the European Union were collected.²

The final dataset used in the underlying paper comprises 254,367 firms, with each record containing financial, industry, and political connection information for the year 2018. Political connections encompass firms that donated to a political party, firms with

¹ See Further Information for details.

² This information is public in Czechia and was scraped from the official websites run by the Ministry of Regional

Development. The datasets were hand cleaned by a private company called Datlab, s.r.o.

board members who donated to a political party, and firms with board members who ran for political office. In 2018, there were 11,850 politically connected firms, constituting 4.65% of the overall sample. Politically connected firms are distributed across all segments of the Czech market, regardless of their financial performance.

The underlying article for this policy brief employed various methods to predict political connections in firms. It began with logistic regression, a widely used technique for binary outcome prediction. Subsequently, four other supervised machine learning methods were applied: ridge regression, Least Absolute Shrinkage and Selection Operator (LASSO), random forests, and random forests with boosting. The performance of each model was evaluated based on prediction accuracy, calculated as the number of correctly classified firms divided by the total number of firms.³

3. Results

The results indicate that over 85% of firms with political connections can be accurately identified by the proposed algorithms (Figure 1). All five models were effective in identifying politically connected firms, with random forests and boosting leading the way, especially when provided with a substantial amount of training data.

Sensitivity (Figure 2) and specificity (Figure 3) analyses showed that the models excelled in correctly identifying politically connected firms, which is particularly crucial from a policy perspective. Boosting and random forests stood out by their ability to accurately predict non-politically connected firms as well, making them valuable tools for policy applications.

³ Additionally, sensitivity and specificity were estimated for each model. Sensitivity measures the proportion of correctly classified politically connected firms among all correctly

The underlying academic article identified several key predictors of political connections in firms. Older companies were more likely to have political ties, likely due to the time needed to establish such connections. Additionally, factors like the value of public procurement contracts, operating revenue, and compliance with reporting requirements played significant roles in predicting political connections. The analyses also emphasized the importance of a combination of various financial and industry indicators rather than a single variable for accurate predictions.

Nevertheless, the underlying article recognizes potential pitfalls, such as algorithmic biases that may disproportionately affect certain types of firms, like foreign-owned companies. Firms may also adapt over time to evade detection, requiring ongoing algorithm updates and the inclusion of random audits for comprehensive coverage.

While the underlying article used interpretable machine learning algorithms, it acknowledges that more complex, less interpretable models such as neural networks could achieve even higher accuracy (Murdoch, Singh, Kumbier, Abbasi-Asl, & Yu, 2019). Despite the absence of some key predictor variables, the research demonstrates that even relatively straightforward algorithms can accurately predict political connections, making them valuable tools for policymakers in combating corruption and conflicts of interest.

4. Policy implications

The policy brief discusses how machine learning algorithms to predict politically

classified firms, while specificity assesses the proportion of correctly classified non-politically connected firms among all correctly classified firms.

connected firms using financial and industry indicators. Performance well exceeded random draws, and even traditional logistic regression models, showcasing their potential in assisting public institutions in identifying firms with significant conflicts of interest arising from political connections.

The implications are significant, as politically connected firms can incur substantial economic and welfare costs for society, including higher product prices, inefficient public works, and lower employment standards (Baranek & Titl, forthcoming; Cingano & Pinotti, 2013; Colonnelli, Prem, & Teso, 2020; Fisman & Wang, 2015; Titl & Geys, 2019). By targeting

these firms for inspection based on machine learning algorithms, these costs could be mitigated. The Ukrainian system 'Dozorro' serves as an inspiring example (Observatory of Public Sector Innovation, 2016), using similar algorithms to detect corruption in public procurement and reporting suspect cases for investigation.

The relevance of the findings extends beyond Czechia, as the algorithm can be applied in most developed countries with only a small sample of connected and non-connected firms and relevant predictors. This approach could significantly increase the efficiency and effectiveness of government agencies combatting corruption.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

References

- Archer, B. (2020, July 9). *Legal proceedings against UK government over awarding of £108m PPE contracts to Antrim firm*. Retrieved from The Irish Times: <https://www.irishnews.com/news/northernirelandnews/2020/07/09/news/legal-proceedings-against-uk-government-over-awarding-of-108m-ppe-contracts-to-antrim-firm-1999417/>
- Baranek, B., & Titl, V. (forthcoming). The Costs of Favoritism in Public Procurement. *Journal of Law and Economics*.
- Cingano, F., & Pinotti, P. (2013). Politicians at work: the private returns and social costs of political connections. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 11(2), 433-465.
- Colonnelli, E., Prem, M., & Teso, E. (2020). Patronage and Selection in Public Sector Organizations. *American Economic Review*, 110(10), 3071-3099.
- Conn, D., & Evans, R. (2020, December 3). *Covid-19 contracts: government refuses to say who benefited from political connections*. Retrieved from The Guardian: <https://www.theguardian.com/world/2020/dec/03/government-secrecy-over-huge-covid-contracts-completely-unnecessary-say-critics>
- Decarolis, F., & Giorgiantonio, C. (2022). Corruption red flags in public procurement: new evidence from Italian calls for tenders. *EPJ Data Science*, 11(16), 1-34.
- Fisman, R., & Wang, Y. (2015). The Mortality Cost of Political Connections. *Review of Economic Studies*, 82(4), 1346-1382.
- Gallego, J., Rivero, G., & Martinez, J. (2021). Preventing rather than punishing: An early warning model of malfeasance in public procurement. *International Journal of Forecasting*, 37, 360-377.
- James, G., Witten, D., Hastie, T., & Tibshirani, R. (2013). *An Introduction to Statistical Learning*. New York: Springer.
- National Audit Office. (2020, November 26). *Investigation into government procurement during the COVID-19 pandemic*. Retrieved from National Audit Office: <https://www.nao.org.uk/report/government-procurement-during-the-covid-19-pandemic/>
- Pegg, D., Lawrence, F., & Conn, D. (2020, November 18). *PPE suppliers with political ties given 'high-priority' status, report reveals*. Retrieved from The Guardian: <https://www.theguardian.com/politics/2020/nov/18/ppe-suppliers-with-political-ties-given-high-priority-status-report-reveals>
- Titl, V., & Geys, B. (2019). Political Donations and the Allocation of Public Procurement Contracts. *European Economic Review*, 111, 443-458.

FIGURE 1: ACCURACY OF PREDICTING POLITICAL CONNECTIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING

Note: The figure can be interpreted as follows: if 5,000 connected firms and 5,000 not connected firms are used to train the algorithm, boosting is 84.1% accurate in predicting which firms are politically connected on a subsample of the same size randomly drawn from the rest of the sample. The figure displays 95% confidence intervals.

FIGURE 2: SENSITIVITY OF PREDICTING POLITICAL CONNECTIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING

Note: The figure can be interpreted as follows: if 5,000 connected firms and 5,000 not connected firms are used to train the algorithm, boosting predicts 87.2% of politically connected firms correctly in a subsample of the same size randomly drawn from the rest of the sample.

FIGURE 3: SPECIFICITY OF PREDICTING POLITICAL CONNECTIONS USING MACHINE LEARNING

Note: The figure can be interpreted as follows: if 5,000 connected firms and 5,000 not connected firms are used to train the algorithm, boosting predicts 81% of not-politically connected firms correctly in a subsample of the same size randomly drawn from the rest of the sample.

Further Information:

Titl V., Mazrekaj D., Schiltz F., (2023) Identifying Politically Connected Firms: A Machine Learning Approach. *Oxford Bulletin of Economics and Statistics*.

<http://doi.org/10.1111/obes.12586>.

DemoTrans is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101059288). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Follow us online www.democracy-transparency.eu

Follow us on Twitter @DemoTrans

Follow us on LinkedIn www.linkedin.com/company/demotrans-project/